

Coevolutionary Federated Learning with Differential Privacy

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Abstract. Training machine learning models on sensitive data is constrained by privacy requirements and limited data sharing. Federated learning keeps data local, but shared updates can still leak information and centralized coordination creates bottlenecks. We propose *Coevolutionary Federated Learning with Differential Privacy (CoEvo-DP)*, a decentralized framework that combines cooperative coevolution of autoencoder components with peer-to-peer parameter exchange and differentially private optimization to provide robust, and privacy-preserving decentralized model training. Clients communicate only with neighbors, eliminating the central server. Experiments on medical image datasets show that *CoEvo-DP* matches or improves reconstruction quality over centralized differentially private federated learning while maintaining comparable resistance to membership inference attacks.

Keywords: Coevolution · Federated Learning · Differential Privacy.

1 Introduction

Organizations use federated learning (FL) [41] to collectively exploit isolated, heterogeneous data sources for machine learning (ML) while overcoming regulatory and technical barriers. In centralized FL, a central server distributes a global model to clients, who train it locally and return their updates; the server aggregates these into a new global model each round, iterating until a stopping criterion is met. However, practical deployments often demand three properties simultaneously: *efficiency* (limiting data transmission and retraining cost), *performance* (producing accurate and robust models), and *security* (resilience and protecting against threats such as data recovery attacks (DRAs) [41, 33]). Centralized FL can struggle to satisfy all three: it introduces a single point of failure, and shared model updates can still leak private information [29].

Cellular evolutionary algorithms (cellular EAs) [11] offer a decentralized alternative, where models are trained across a cellular substrate such as a ring or two-dimensional lattice. Each client exchanges model parameters only with local neighbors each round, eliminating the central coordinator. This scales linearly in communication cost as clients are added, and naturally supports heterogeneous

hyperparameters across clients. The two paradigms differ significantly in their communication architecture, and the choice between them depends on the goals of the training. When efficiency, performance, and security must all be satisfied, the decentralized structure of cellular EAs is a natural starting point, but it must be extended to address DRAs on shared model parameters.

Specifically, we address the following research questions: **RQ1** What are the efficiency, performance, and security impacts of *CoEvo-DP* training with differential privacy (DP) against data recovery attacks? **RQ2** What is the impact of ANN architecture on the training? **RQ3** How does the choice of network topology (e.g., varying the ring radius) affect training?

We propose *Coevolutionary Federated Learning with Differential Privacy* (*CoEvo-DP*), extending the coevolutionary autoencoder framework of Lipi-AE [10] with differential privacy (DP) to produce a flexible, efficient, and privacy-preserving training framework. *CoEvo-DP* coevolves multiple populations of autoencoder (AE) components leveraging isolation, heterogeneity, and dynamism to improve resilience, while DP protects against DRAs on shared updates. Fig. 1 illustrates the overall system: clients arranged in a ring topology each maintain a local population of encoder-decoder pairs, exchange center models with neighbors, and train locally with DP. We empirically evaluate *CoEvo-DP* on medical imaging data, a domain where privacy constraints are both strict and well-motivated.

Fig. 1: Overview of *CoEvo-DP* with an example of four clients arranged in a ring topology. Each client maintains a local population of encoder-decoder pairs. Local model parameters are shared with neighboring clients, and each client selects the best encoder-decoder combination from its neighborhood, trains it with differential privacy, and updates its local population.

The contributions of this paper are: first, it introduces *CoEvo-DP*, a decentralized cooperative coevolutionary framework for training autoencoders under DP local optimization. Second, it analyzes the communication, resilience, and privacy implications of replacing server aggregation with local neighborhood exchange. Third, it empirically compares *CoEvo-DP* with local, centralized FL, and non-private coevolutionary baselines on medical image reconstruction and reconstruction-based membership inference attacks.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 discusses background and related work. Section 3 describes *CoEvo-DP* in detail. Section 4 presents the empirical experiments. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and outlines future work.

2 Background & Related Work

CoEvo-DP combines three main components: peer-to-peer model exchange, cooperative coevolution of autoencoder components, and DP.

2.1 Preliminaries

Federated Learning FL trains a shared model across clients without centralizing raw data. Formally, clients collectively minimize $\min_{\theta} \sum_i \frac{|\mathcal{D}_i|}{|\mathcal{D}|} \mathcal{L}_i(\theta)$, where \mathcal{L}_i is the local loss on client i 's private dataset \mathcal{D}_i . The canonical solution, FedAvg [19], has a coordinator broadcast θ , collect locally updated parameters, and aggregate them each round. Key challenges are data heterogeneity, system heterogeneity, and security, e.g. the coordinator is a single point of failure.

There are alternatives that remove the coordinator entirely by organizing clients as nodes \mathcal{V} in a communication graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ [18, 38]. Each client i maintains its own parameters θ_i and exchanges updates only with immediate neighbors $\mathcal{N}(i) = \{j : (i, j) \in \mathcal{E}\}$ via local mixing, e.g., $\theta_i \leftarrow \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i) \cup \{i\}} w_{ij} \theta_j$, where w_{ij} form a doubly stochastic matrix ensuring global consensus over time. The topology of \mathcal{G} directly governs the convergence–communication tradeoff: a *ring* connects each client to exactly two neighbors, minimizing communication but requiring $O(n)$ hops to propagate information across n clients. Denser graphs mix faster but approach the communication burden of centralized FL. Decentralized FL eliminates single points of failure, but introduces design challenges around topology selection, heterogeneous local computation, and security assumptions on peer communication [38].

Differential Privacy DP provides a formal guarantee that the output of a computation is nearly indistinguishable whether or not any single individual's data is included [6]. Formally, a randomized mechanism \mathcal{M} satisfies (ϵ, δ) -DP if for any two datasets D, D' differing in one record and any measurable output set S :

$$\Pr[\mathcal{M}(D) \in S] \leq e^{\epsilon} \Pr[\mathcal{M}(D') \in S] + \delta,$$

where $\epsilon \geq 0$ controls the privacy loss budget and $\delta \geq 0$ is a small failure probability. Smaller ϵ means stronger privacy, at the cost of more noise and typically lower utility. In deep learning, DP-SGD operationalizes this by clipping per-sample gradients to norm C and adding Gaussian noise $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 C^2 \mathbf{I})$ before each update [1], with privacy cost tracked via Rényi DP accounting [21]. In FL, DP can be applied at client level to protect shared updates [9] or at user level during federated averaging [20]. These approaches motivate integrating DP into generative training loops, but they rarely examine the additional instability and privacy-utility tension that arises in decentralized peer-to-peer settings.

Data Recovery Attacks on Shared Models Despite keeping raw data local, FL and decentralized FL can leak sensitive information through shared gradients or model parameters [33]. Membership inference attacks determine whether a specific record was used in training [27], while gradient inversion attacks reconstruct training examples directly from shared gradients [42, 8]. White-box attacks further amplify these threats, with access to intermediate representations in FL [22]. In addition, for generative models reconstruction attacks against autoencoders can expose whether specific records influenced the model [12]. Defenses range from update shaping to information-theoretic bounds [28, 29], but often trade privacy for utility and can be brittle across architectures and datasets.

Autoencoders An autoencoder (AE) consists of two components: an encoder $f_\phi : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Z}$ that compresses an input x into a lower-dimensional latent representation $z = f_\phi(x)$, and a decoder $g_\psi : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ that reconstructs the original input from z . Training minimizes a reconstruction loss:

$$\mathcal{L}(\phi, \psi) = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mathcal{D}} [\|x - g_\psi(f_\phi(x))\|^2].$$

The result is a compact, learned representation of the data manifold. A variational autoencoder is a generative model with a prior and noise distribution [17].

Coevolutionary Algorithms for Robust Model Training Coevolutionary algorithms evolve multiple interacting populations simultaneously. In cooperative coevolution, the problem is decomposed into subcomponents, each maintained as a separate population P_k , whose individuals are evaluated jointly by combining them with representatives from other populations [23]. Formally, the fitness of $\theta^{(k)} \in P_k$ is assessed by pairing it with collaborators drawn from $\{P_j\}_{j \neq k}$. Evolutionary strategies and population-based training extend this to scalable search over neural network parameters and hyperparameters [26, 13]. Spatially structured coevolution limits selection pressure to local neighborhoods in \mathcal{G} , stabilizing training and preserving diversity [11, 30]. This spatial structure has been used to train AEs efficiently by coevolving and selecting encoder-decoder combinations [10], with pruning-aware operators further guiding evolutionary search [16]. A broader treatment of distributed spatial coevolution appears in [31].

2.2 Related Work

Prior work has studied DP-FL, decentralized FL, privacy attacks, and evolutionary approaches to federated optimization, but these lines have rarely been combined for differentially private coevolutionary training of generative models (see Table 1). Work that explicitly combines FL with evolutionary computation is emerging. EvoFed replaces gradient exchange with fitness-based information sharing via synchronized evolution strategies, reducing communication overhead [25]. Neuroevolution has been adapted to federated settings with decentralized coordination, enabling heterogeneous neural architectures [3]. In privacy-preserving evolutionary optimization, DP mechanisms have been formalized for federated surrogate-assisted evolutionary algorithms [34], with broader

surveys connecting privacy mechanisms to federated evolutionary optimization pipelines [24, 40]. For generative models, federated generative autoencoders have been explored for privacy-preserving data collection [15], and systematic reviews identify open challenges around privacy, evaluation, and non-IID stability in federated generative modeling [7].

Table 1: Comparison of related work. **Decent.**: decentralized; **Coev.**: coevolutionary training; **DP**: DP mechanism integrated into training; **DRA defense**: explicit defense against data recovery or membership inference attacks.

Work	Decent.	Coev.	DP	Attack defense	Model
FedAvg [19]	×	×	×	×	Any
D-PSGD [18]	✓	×	×	×	Any
DP-FedAvg [20]	×	×	✓	✓	Discriminative
Client DP-FL [9]	×	×	✓	✓	Discriminative
Soteria [28]	×	×	×	✓	Discriminative
Spatial coev. [11]	✓	✓	×	×	GAN
Coev. AE [10]	✓	✓	×	×	Autoencoder
Fed. AE [15]	×	×	✓	×	Autoencoder
EvoFed [25]	×	×	×	×	Any
NEvoFed [3]	✓	×	×	×	Any
<i>CoEvo-DP</i> (this work)	✓	✓	✓	✓	AE

Nevertheless, a gap remains: evaluating how decentralized coevolutionary training of generative models interacts with DP under data reconstruction attacks. *CoEvo-DP* targets this gap by combining decentralized neighborhood mixing, cooperative coevolution of AEs, and DP.

3 Method

CoEvo-DP builds upon Lipi-AE [10,11], a cooperative coevolutionary framework, and extends it with differential privacy for distributed ANN training to resist data recovery attacks. The approach is decentralized: clients are arranged in a topology, here ring, and communicate only with local neighbors. Figure 1 provides an overview of *CoEvo-DP*.

3.1 *CoEvo-DP*

CoEvo-DP trains ANN pairs (encoder e and decoder d) across a ring of N cells. Each cell $k \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ maintains a center pair (e_k, d_k) . At each generation, a cell forms a neighborhood subpopulation by collecting the center pairs from neighboring cells within radius r , giving a neighborhood of size $2r + 1$.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, after each generation, the updated center pair (e_k, d_k) is shared with neighboring cells. For example, Fig. 1 shows four cells arranged in a ring with $r = 1$, where the neighborhood of each cell is shaded gray.

At each generation $t \in \{1, \dots, T\}$, each cell executes Algorithm 1. The cell first collects center pairs from its neighbors to form a subpopulation. Cooperative fitness is evaluated using the best-case solution concept [10]: the cross-pair

loss matrix $L_{ij} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{recon}}(e_i, d_j)$ is computed over all combinations to form a candidate pool. The fitness of each encoder (resp. decoder) is then $\phi(e_k) = \min_j L_{kj}$ (resp. $\phi(d_k) = \min_i L_{ki}$). Tournament selection picks a new center pair from a random subset of the encoders and a decoder in the candidate pool ranked by fitness (loss). The selected pair is trained with Stochastic Gradient Descent. For DP, gradients are clipped to norm C and Gaussian noise of scale σ is added at each step, with privacy accounting via the Rényi Differential Privacy (RDP) accountant [21]. After training, the pair becomes the new center. After T generations, *CoEvo-DP* selects the globally optimal pair based on training loss.

Algorithm 1: *CoEvo-DP*: update cell k at generation t

Input: Cells $\{(e_i, d_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, cell index k , radius r , tournament size τ , DP parameters (C, σ)

- 1 $\mathbf{P}_e \leftarrow \{e_k\}; \mathbf{P}_d \leftarrow \{d_k\}$
- 2 **foreach** $j \in \{(k \pm i) \bmod N \mid i = 1, \dots, r\}$ **do**
- 3 | $\mathbf{P}_e \leftarrow \mathbf{P}_e \cup \{e_j\}; \mathbf{P}_d \leftarrow \mathbf{P}_d \cup \{d_j\}$ // collect neighbors
- 4 Compute $L_{ij} = \mathcal{L}(e_i, d_j, B), \forall (e_i, d_j) \in \mathbf{P}_e \times \mathbf{P}_d$ // cross-pair evaluation
- 5 $\phi(e_i) \leftarrow \min_j L_{ij}; \phi(d_j) \leftarrow \min_i L_{ij}$ // best-case fitness
- 6 $(e_k, d_k) \leftarrow \text{tournament_select}(\mathbf{P}_e, \mathbf{P}_d, \phi, \tau)$ // find new center pair
- 7 **foreach** $\text{batch } B \in \mathcal{D}_k$ **do**
- 8 | $\nabla_e, \nabla_d \leftarrow \nabla_{\text{DP}(C, \sigma)} \mathcal{L}(e_k, d_k, B)$ // DP-clipped gradients
- 9 | $(e_k, d_k) \leftarrow \text{optimizer}(e_k, d_k, \nabla_e, \nabla_d)$ // parameter update
- 10 $(e_k, d_k) \leftarrow \arg \min \mathcal{L}(e_k, d_k, B)$ // set best pair at center

3.2 Method Analysis

We analyze *CoEvo-DP* with respect to: resilience, communication efficiency, and security. A computational efficiency analysis of Lipi-AE is in [11, 10].

Resilience: The decentralized ring topology ensures that model sharing can continue until all cells are isolated. This contrasts with centralized FL, where the failure of the central server halts model sharing entirely.

Communication efficiency: In centralized FL with n clients, the server bandwidth per round is $\mathcal{O}(n)$, which grows with the number of clients and becomes a bottleneck, for a total of $\mathcal{O}(nT)$ over T rounds. In *CoEvo-DP*, each node communicates only with its $2r$ neighbors, so the maximum per-node bandwidth per generation is $\mathcal{O}(2r)$, constant with respect to n , for a total of $\mathcal{O}(n2rT)$ over T generations. Note that while *CoEvo-DP* increases total encrypted transmissions by a factor of $2r$ compared to centralized FL, the encryption burden is distributed evenly across nodes rather than concentrated at a server bottleneck.

Security: Differential privacy bounds the influence of any individual training sample on the model parameters, limiting data recovery attacks. The per-step gradient clipping and noise addition [1] provide formal (ϵ, δ) -DP guarantees. Gradient inversion attacks [41, 42, 39] reconstruct training data from shared gradients, relying on direct access to individual client updates. In centralized FL, a server with access to updates can observe such updates. In *CoEvo-DP*, updates

are fragmented across nodes and time: each cell trains only a local encoder-decoder pair on a fraction of the data, so an attacker must collect and align updates across multiple nodes and generations to reconstruct signals, increasing the attack complexity. DP further degrades gradient informativeness via clipping and noise addition, making inversion impractical.

4 Experiments

With *CoEvo-DP* we empirically evaluate the efficiency, performance, and security of decentralized coevolutionary ANN training with differential privacy against data recovery attacks (**RQ1**), and analyze the impact of ANN architecture (**RQ2**). We first describe the experimental setup, then analyze the results.

4.1 Setup

We train autoencoders (AEs) with cooperative coevolution on MedMNIST 2D [35, 36], a benchmark of standardized medical imaging datasets. Table 2 reports the image type, resolution, and train/validation/test sizes. We additionally evaluate on the larger RetinaMNIST variant at 224×224 pixels to assess scalability to higher-resolution inputs.

Table 2: Datasets used in experiments, all from MedMNIST 2D.

Dataset	Type	Resolution	Train	Val	Test
PneumoniaMNIST	Greyscale	28×28	4,708	524	624
OrganCMNIST	Greyscale	28×28	12,975	2,392	8,216
RetinaMNIST	RGB	28×28	1,080	120	400
DermaMNIST	RGB	28×28	7,007	1,003	2,005
RetinaMNIST (large)	RGB	224×224	1,080	120	400

Architectures We evaluate Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) AEs. The **MLP** encoder flattens the input, maps it to a 1024-dimensional hidden representation with ReLU, and projects it deterministically to a 64-dimensional latent space through two heads for μ and $\log \sigma^2$; the decoder mirrors this structure. The MLP is used only for 28×28 images. The **CNN** uses symmetric encoder-decoder pairs with transposed convolutions. For 28×28 images, it uses two convolutional layers with 32 and 64 channels; for 224×224 , it uses five layers ($8 \rightarrow 16 \rightarrow 32 \rightarrow 64 \rightarrow 64$), both reaching a 7×7 feature map before the latent projection.

Threat Model We consider membership inference attacks (MIA), where an adversary attempts to infer whether a sample was used for training. Privacy is evaluated with a reconstruction-based MIA [33], which uses reconstruction loss as the attack signal, exploiting the tendency of AEs to reconstruct training samples with lower error than unseen samples.

Experimental Design We evaluate six configurations that differ in training topology and use of DP, as summarized in Table 3. The primary comparison is between centralized DP-FL and the proposed decentralized DP coevolutionary setting. Client datasets are constructed using an IID partition of the corresponding training set, so that each client samples from the same underlying data distribution.

Table 3: Experimental configurations.

Configuration	Training	DP	Description
ae	Local only	×	Baseline: single AE, no federation
ae-dp	Local only	✓	Baseline with DP
ae-fl	Centralized FL	×	FedAvg (Flower [2]), no DP
ae-dp-fl	Centralized FL	✓	FedAvg with DP
ae-lipi	Lipi-AE [10]	×	Decentralized coevolution, no DP
ae-lipi-dp	<i>CoEvo-DP</i>	✓	Decentralized coevolution with DP (proposed)

DP is implemented with Opacus [37], using $\delta = 1/|\mathcal{D}_k|$, where $|\mathcal{D}_k|$ is the local training set size of client k . The same clipping norm, noise multiplier, and δ rule are used for centralized FL and *CoEvo-DP*, ensuring identical privacy budgets. For compute-fairness, centralized FL uses R rounds and E local epochs such that $R \times E$ equals the number of *CoEvo-DP* generations, matching the total local optimization steps per client. The resulting ϵ values computed with the Rényi DP accountant over the full training schedule for each dataset are: 122 for PneumoniaMNIST, 100 for OrganCMNIST and 158 for RetinaMNIST. Table 4 reports the hyperparameters.

Reconstruction quality is evaluated on test images over 25 independent runs using mean squared error (MSE), structural similarity index measure (SSIM) [32], peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), and normalized mutual information (NMI), which are commonly used for medical image assessment [4, 5, 14]. Privacy is evaluated using MIA AUC and the true positive rate at low false positive rates, TPR@1% and TPR@5%. MIA AUC measures the overall ability of the attacker to distinguish training from non-training samples, with values close to 0.5 indicating random-guessing performance, while TPR@1% and TPR@5% quantify attack success in high-confidence regimes. Statistical significance is analyzed using Welch two-sample t -tests at $\alpha = 0.01$ with Holm correction.

4.2 Results and Analysis

This section analyzes the experimental behavior of *CoEvo-DP* from three perspectives: *i*) comparing *CoEvo-DP* against centralized DP-FL to evaluate the privacy–utility trade-off; *ii*) studying how DP and network architecture affect reconstruction quality and membership-inference resistance; and *iii*) analyzing how the coevolutionary parameters (i.e., neighborhood radius r and tournament size τ) affect signal propagation, selection pressure, and population diversity.

To illustrate the different optimization behavior of local, centralized federated, and coevolutionary training under DP and non-DP settings, we focus on

Table 4: Experimental hyperparameter configurations.

Parameter	Value
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate	0.0001
Epochs	100
Batch size	64
Loss	Mean Squared Error (MSE)
FL & <i>CoEvo-DP</i> clients	4
DP noise multiplier	0.3
DP max gradient norm	5.0
DP δ	$1/ \mathcal{D}_k $
Centralized FL rounds (R)	25
Centralized FL local epochs (E)	4
Centralized FL aggregation	Average
<i>CoEvo-DP</i> generations	100
<i>CoEvo-DP</i> topology	Ring (radius 1)
<i>CoEvo-DP</i> aggregation	Min

training dynamics on RetinaMNIST. Fig. 2 illustrates the different optimization dynamics on RetinaMNIST. Non-private methods (`ae`, `ae-fl`, and `ae-lipi`) converge to lower losses, while DP variants stabilize at higher losses due to clipping and noise. *CoEvo-DP* exhibits stronger oscillations than centralized DP-FL because encoder-decoder pairs are repeatedly selected and replaced, but it reaches a comparable final loss.

Fig. 2: Training loss evolution on RetinaMNIST.

Privacy-utility trade-off and comparison with centralized DP-FL. Tables 5–8 report the reconstruction and MIA results for PneumoniaMNIST, RetinaMNIST, OrganCMNIST, and the high-resolution RetinaMNIST setting. For reconstruction, lower error values are better, while higher SSIM, PSNR, and NMI are better. For MIA, AUC values close to 0.5 indicate random-guessing attack behavior; therefore, results are reported as $\Delta_{\text{MIA}} = |\text{MIA AUC} - 0.5|$. Lower TPR values at fixed FPR indicate fewer confident membership detections. In these ta-

bles, MSE, SSIM, TPR@1%, and TPR@5% are reported in units of 10^{-2} , while PSNR and NMI are kept in original units; \uparrow means higher is better and \downarrow indicates lower is better. Figs. 4–7 in Appendix A summarize the main statistical test results.

Table 5: Results on PneumoniaMNIST. Values are reported as mean (normalized standard deviation in %).

Setup	Image Reconstruction				MIA Evaluation		
	MSE \downarrow	SSIM \uparrow	PSNR \uparrow	NMI \uparrow	$\Delta_{\text{MIA}}\downarrow$	TPR@1% \downarrow	TPR@5% \downarrow
<i>MLP Architecture</i>							
ae	0.21(2.75)	84.48(0.36)	26.85(0.55)	1.37(0.04)	0.05(5.92)	1.75(34.85)	8.94(8.96)
ae-dp	1.09(2.17)	60.67(1.30)	19.63(0.44)	1.35(0.07)	0.01(20.36)	0.13(261.77)	4.62(11.66)
ae-fl	0.47(2.26)	76.51(0.37)	23.28(0.41)	1.36(0.03)	0.01(74.32)	1.62(33.49)	5.12(4.03)
ae-dp-fl	1.56(0.11)	53.02(0.18)	18.08(0.02)	1.35(0.07)	0.03(7.75)	0.44(97.49)	4.04(8.38)
ae-lipi	0.35(7.26)	79.71(0.63)	24.53(1.32)	1.37(0.10)	0.02(15.98)	1.94(31.77)	5.62(40.84)
<i>CoEvo-DP</i>	1.52(0.42)	53.75(0.23)	18.20(0.11)	1.35(0.16)	0.03(7.24)	0.34(58.55)	3.38(5.98)
<i>CNN Architecture</i>							
ae	0.15(4.71)	87.59(0.34)	28.36(0.74)	1.38(0.10)	0.05(5.87)	1.90(49.36)	7.95(12.63)
ae-dp	0.62(10.88)	66.81(1.84)	22.09(1.77)	1.35(0.10)	0.01(26.59)	0.73(64.21)	4.67(21.44)
ae-fl	0.34(6.99)	77.71(1.39)	24.78(1.38)	1.36(0.11)	0.03(17.67)	0.78(54.86)	4.55(13.96)
ae-dp-fl	1.44(7.29)	53.64(0.64)	18.43(1.73)	1.35(0.16)	0.02(25.27)	0.43(76.88)	3.25(9.08)
ae-lipi	0.25(7.25)	81.99(1.41)	26.09(1.05)	1.37(0.19)	0.04(8.67)	1.03(41.65)	6.65(18.13)
<i>CoEvo-DP</i>	1.03(11.85)	57.72(2.35)	19.89(2.25)	1.35(0.13)	0.01(96.08)	0.38(90.60)	3.05(21.50)

Table 6: Results on OrganCMNIST. Values are reported as mean (normalized standard deviation in %).

Setup	Image Reconstruction				MIA Evaluation		
	MSE \downarrow	SSIM \uparrow	PSNR \uparrow	NMI \uparrow	$\Delta_{\text{MIA}}\downarrow$	TPR@1% \downarrow	TPR@5% \downarrow
<i>MLP Architecture</i>							
ae	1.51(0.23)	52.70(0.16)	18.21(0.03)	1.32(0.03)	0.03(13.42)	0.62(30.69)	2.81(7.51)
ae-dp	3.25(1.88)	20.45(1.74)	14.89(0.44)	1.30(0.06)	0.08(2.92)	0.81(74.91)	2.62(7.77)
ae-fl	1.96(0.39)	40.70(0.57)	17.09(0.11)	1.31(0.02)	0.07(2.42)	3.51(5.90)	2.75(11.72)
ae-dp-fl	5.17(1.71)	14.39(0.96)	12.88(0.56)	1.29(0.07)	0.07(2.88)	0.44(44.30)	2.06(17.89)
ae-lipi	1.72(2.02)	46.93(1.72)	17.66(0.43)	1.31(0.06)	0.07(7.41)	3.24(13.07)	2.94(11.82)
<i>CoEvo-DP</i>	4.40(0.56)	16.25(1.03)	13.57(0.20)	1.29(0.05)	0.07(7.10)	0.25(193.57)	1.62(25.10)
<i>CNN Architecture</i>							
ae	1.39(1.60)	56.01(0.92)	18.58(0.34)	1.33(0.21)	0.07(14.00)	0.25(0.00)	3.17(16.94)
ae-dp	2.05(1.87)	38.49(1.61)	16.88(0.47)	1.31(0.04)	0.10(2.80)	0.10(212.96)	2.60(11.66)
ae-fl	1.63(2.62)	48.97(2.71)	17.88(0.77)	1.32(0.14)	0.09(2.27)	0.20(82.61)	2.40(37.29)
ae-dp-fl	2.84(2.39)	25.11(3.25)	15.47(0.80)	1.30(0.10)	0.10(4.43)	0.33(57.85)	2.40(10.36)
ae-lipi	1.49(2.71)	53.40(2.22)	18.28(0.73)	1.32(0.09)	0.09(4.64)	0.25(0.00)	2.33(34.79)
<i>CoEvo-DP</i>	2.34(2.03)	32.49(2.33)	16.31(0.59)	1.30(0.05)	0.10(1.48)	0.09(322.94)	2.25(20.38)

The reconstruction results in Tables 5–8 show a consistent trend. Under the same DP mechanism, *CoEvo-DP* generally improves over centralized DP-FL (**ae-dp-fl**) on the main reconstruction metrics, especially MSE, SSIM, and PSNR. The Holm-corrected tests support this trend across most dataset-architecture combinations, with the strongest evidence on the error-based and perceptual reconstruction metrics. The advantage is particularly visible in CNN settings and in the high-resolution RetinaMNIST experiment, where centralized DP-FL suffers stronger degradation under DP noise. NMI is more nuanced, with a few cases in which the difference is not significant or favors **ae-dp-fl**; nevertheless, the overall reconstruction evidence supports *CoEvo-DP* as the stronger

Table 7: Results on RetinaMNIST. Values are reported as mean (normalized standard deviation in %).

Setup	Image Reconstruction				MIA Evaluation		
	MSE↓	SSIM↑	PSNR↑	NMI↑	$\Delta_{\text{MIA}} \downarrow$	TPR@1%↓	TPR@5%↓
<i>MLP Architecture</i>							
ae	0.21(4.06)	85.63(0.41)	26.69(0.67)	1.33(0.11)	0.03(33.99)	1.75(40.62)	6.19(40.19)
ae-dp	2.35(0.60)	61.97(0.18)	16.32(0.18)	1.28(0.07)	0.03(1.99)	0.69(30.53)	3.19(25.58)
ae-fl	1.12(7.85)	74.84(1.16)	19.53(1.76)	1.30(0.18)	0.02(69.14)	2.12(61.99)	6.75(14.36)
ae-dp-fl	2.52(0.58)	57.99(0.49)	16.00(0.20)	1.26(0.27)	0.03(9.94)	0.60(45.57)	3.76(50.71)
ae-lipi	0.75(21.73)	78.88(1.54)	21.30(3.71)	1.31(0.11)	0.02(80.28)	2.06(45.54)	6.50(41.29)
<i>CoEvo-DP</i>	2.43(0.81)	59.98(0.15)	16.16(0.21)	1.27(0.15)	0.03(4.07)	0.51(40.69)	3.38(48.37)
<i>CNN Architecture</i>							
ae	0.20(2.27)	84.59(0.29)	27.09(0.47)	1.32(0.13)	0.02(15.20)	1.75(63.44)	7.60(14.99)
ae-dp	1.99(3.31)	60.57(1.21)	17.03(0.98)	1.26(0.17)	0.03(7.60)	1.20(25.45)	2.90(39.91)
ae-fl	0.50(13.95)	74.46(2.20)	23.06(2.27)	1.28(0.39)	0.01(143.20)	1.98(38.22)	6.78(20.00)
ae-dp-fl	6.57(25.85)	12.95(32.33)	11.90(12.34)	1.16(1.28)	0.05(19.51)	1.20(58.78)	4.15(29.70)
ae-lipi	0.38(8.48)	77.98(1.04)	24.19(1.32)	1.29(0.30)	0.01(81.67)	2.77(38.29)	7.88(13.49)
<i>CoEvo-DP</i>	2.33(3.28)	48.66(8.00)	16.35(0.94)	1.23(0.63)	0.03(7.58)	1.10(64.70)	3.77(42.36)

Table 8: Results on large RetinaMNIST (224×224 px). Values are reported as mean (normalized standard deviation in %).

Setup	Image Reconstruction				MIA Evaluation		
	MSE↓	SSIM↑	PSNR↑	NMI↑	$\Delta_{\text{MIA}} \downarrow$	TPR@1%↓	TPR@5%↓
ae	0.33(12.19)	78.34(2.55)	24.81(2.15)	1.25(0.60)	0.02(58.85)	2.42(10.24)	7.17(20.38)
ae-dp	5.81(5.76)	44.00(6.44)	12.37(2.24)	1.11(3.81)	0.04(1.19)	1.17(20.50)	3.58(37.48)
ae-fl	1.23(11.68)	54.62(5.69)	19.11(2.78)	1.17(0.93)	0.04(2.18)	1.75(65.90)	5.58(19.78)
ae-dp-fl	10.97(16.35)	41.16(8.68)	9.61(8.28)	1.05(0.69)	0.01(133.66)	1.25(50.56)	3.83(41.23)
ae-lipi	0.76(5.20)	60.76(16.75)	21.20(1.03)	1.20(0.91)	0.03(12.36)	1.75(37.24)	8.08(33.61)
<i>CoEvo-DP</i>	6.82(4.39)	36.63(6.80)	11.67(1.83)	1.06(0.59)	0.05(0.95)	1.12(37.00)	3.22(6.60)

distributed DP training strategy. The absolute SSIM values on OrganCMNIST are lower than on the other 28×28 datasets, indicating that this dataset is a more difficult reconstruction task for the evaluated AE architectures.

The privacy results are less uniform than the reconstruction results. *CoEvo-DP* often obtains comparable low-FPR attack behavior, particularly for TPR@1%FPR and TPR@5%FPR, and in several cases improves the low-FPR TPR over *ae-dp-fl*. However, Δ_{MIA} does not consistently favor *CoEvo-DP*. In particular, some CNN settings, including PneumoniaMNIST and RetinaMNIST, favor centralized DP-FL in terms of MIA AUC deviation from random guessing. Several AUC values are also close to, or below, 0.5, which should be interpreted cautiously: such values do not necessarily indicate stronger privacy, but rather that reconstruction loss is not consistently aligned with successful membership discrimination in those settings. Thus, the privacy evidence does not support claiming that *CoEvo-DP* is uniformly more private than centralized DP-FL.

The broader ranking also reflects the expected effect of DP. Non-private training, especially the local AE baseline, usually provides the best reconstruction quality because it is not affected by gradient clipping, Gaussian noise, or aggregation constraints. The non-private federated and coevolutionary variants remain below the local AE but above their DP counterparts. Among private methods, the local DP baseline often preserves relatively strong reconstruction

quality because it avoids cross-client aggregation, whereas the main comparison in this paper is between `ae-dp-f1` and *CoEvo-DP*, which share the same DP mechanism but differ in coordination structure. These results suggest that coevolutionary neighborhood selection partly compensates for DP-induced optimization noise by repeatedly selecting and propagating better-performing encoder-decoder pairs within local neighborhoods.

These results answer **RQ1**: *CoEvo-DP* improves reconstruction quality over centralized DP-FL under matched DP settings while maintaining broadly comparable empirical resistance to reconstruction-based membership inference attacks. The evidence supports a utility advantage under privacy constraints, but not a claim of uniformly stronger privacy.

Effect of differential privacy. For all datasets and architectures, the non-private configurations obtain the best reconstruction quality. Adding DP increases reconstruction error and reduces SSIM and PSNR, as expected from DP-SGD, which clips gradients and injects Gaussian noise into the optimization process.

Both *CoEvo-DP* and `ae-dp-f1` suffer a reduction in reconstruction quality compared with their non-private counterparts. However, the loss of utility is larger for `ae-dp-f1` than for *CoEvo-DP* in several cases. This suggests that the coevolutionary selection mechanism can partly compensate for noisy local optimization by promoting better-performing encoder-decoder pairs across neighboring clients.

The MIA results show that DP generally reduces the effectiveness of the reconstruction-loss attack, particularly in the low-FPR regime. The non-private methods often obtain AUC values above random guessing and higher TPR values at low FPR. In contrast, the DP methods tend to reduce confident membership detections, although MIA AUC is not uniformly improved across all datasets and architectures. Thus, DP provides the main privacy protection mechanism, while the coevolutionary topology primarily affects the utility obtained under that privacy constraint.

Effect of network architecture. Tables 5–6 compare MLP and CNN autoencoders on the 28×28 datasets. Tables 9–11 in Appendix A report the direct statistical comparison between these two AE architectures.

CNNs are significantly better than MLPs in most reconstruction comparisons, especially for MSE and PSNR, where CNNs outperform MLPs in 17 out of 18 comparisons.

For *CoEvo-DP*, the architecture effect is also mostly favorable to CNNs. On OrganCMNIST, *CoEvo-DP* with CNN significantly improves MSE, SSIM, PSNR, and NMI over the MLP variant. On PneumoniaMNIST, *CoEvo-DP* with CNN significantly improves MSE, SSIM, and PSNR. RetinaMNIST is more nuanced: CNN improves MSE and PSNR, whereas MLP obtains higher SSIM and NMI.

The privacy metrics show a less consistent architecture effect. For *CoEvo-DP*, the MIA AUC differences between MLP and CNN are significant on all three datasets, but the direction is dataset-dependent: the MLP variant is closer

to random guessing on OrganCMNIST, whereas the CNN variant is closer to random guessing on PneumoniaMNIST and RetinaMNIST. The low-FPR metrics are also mixed. On OrganCMNIST, *CoEvo-DP* with CNN obtains a lower TPR@1%FPR, but the difference is not significant, while the MLP variant obtains a significantly lower TPR@5%FPR. On PneumoniaMNIST, the differences in TPR@1%FPR and TPR@5%FPR are not significant. On RetinaMNIST, the MLP variant obtains a significantly lower TPR@1%FPR, while TPR@5%FPR is not significantly different. Thus, unlike reconstruction quality, the privacy metrics do not show a systematic advantage for either architecture.

These results answer **RQ2**: CNN autoencoders are generally more effective than MLP autoencoders for error-based image reconstruction metrics, including under differentially private *CoEvo-DP* training. This architecture advantage does not extend uniformly to the privacy metrics, where MLP and CNN variants show mixed and dataset-dependent membership-inference behavior.

Effect of topology and selection pressure. The coevolutionary behavior of *CoEvo-DP* is controlled by two main parameters: the ring radius r and the tournament size τ . The radius determines the size of the local neighborhood from which candidate encoder–decoder components are collected, and therefore regulates signal propagation and communication cost. The tournament size controls selection pressure within each neighborhood, determining how strongly better-performing components are favored over weaker alternatives. Together, these parameters govern the balance between propagation speed, population diversity, communication overhead, and exploitation pressure.

Appendix B provides a detailed analysis of these effects on DermaMNIST. When r is increased with fixed $\tau = 2$, reconstruction metrics such as MSE and PSNR improve slightly, but encoder–decoder diversity decreases. This indicates that wider neighborhoods accelerate the spread of useful components across clients, while also homogenizing the population. Similarly, increasing τ at fixed radii strengthens selection pressure: better-performing encoder–decoder pairs are promoted more aggressively, which generally improves or preserves reconstruction quality but reduces the number of alternative solutions that remain active in the population.

Fig. 3: Radius and tournament size analysis on OrganCMNIST with 40 clients.

Figure 3 complements the appendix analysis with a larger 40-client setting on OrganCMNIST, where signal propagation through the ring topology becomes more critical. In this setting, larger radii consistently reduce MSE, and increasing τ also improves reconstruction quality. This suggests that, as the number of clients grows, wider neighborhoods and stronger selection pressure help high-quality encoder–decoder components propagate more quickly through the population.

Taken together, the appendix results and Figure 3 show that r and τ control the exploration–exploitation trade-off of *CoEvo-DP*. Small radii and moderate tournament sizes preserve locality, diversity, communication efficiency, and the decentralized nature of the method, but propagate high-quality components more slowly. Larger radii and stronger tournaments improve exploitation and can increase reconstruction quality, but reduce diversity and increase communication. This answers **RQ3**: the ring radius and tournament size directly affect the quality–diversity–communication trade-off in *CoEvo-DP*.

Summary of findings. *CoEvo-DP* improves reconstruction quality over centralized DP-FL under the same DP mechanism, while maintaining comparable reconstruction-based MIA resistance. DP introduces the expected utility loss, but coevolutionary selection partly compensates by propagating stronger encoder-decoder combinations. Finally, radius and tournament size expose a clear quality-diversity-communication trade-off.

5 Conclusion & Future Work

We presented *CoEvo-DP*, a privacy-preserving decentralized machine learning framework that combines cooperative coevolutionary training of autoencoders with differential privacy. By organizing clients in a ring topology, *CoEvo-DP* eliminates the central coordinator that is both a bottleneck and a single point of failure in standard federated learning.

Across multiple MedMNIST datasets and two network architectures (MLP and CNN), *CoEvo-DP* matches or outperforms centralized FL with DP in reconstruction quality while maintaining equivalent membership inference resistance. CNN architectures consistently outperform MLP encoders, and this advantage is preserved under gradient noise. Analysis of ring radius and tournament size confirms that more localized configurations better preserve population diversity and structural similarity, whereas wider neighborhoods improve error-based reconstruction metrics at the cost of homogeneity.

Two directions stand out for future work. First, the framework extends naturally to other modalities such as time series and graph-structured data. Additionally, more diverse topologies such as 2D lattice could be explored as an alternative to the ring topology.

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A Statistical significance results

This appendix includes the main statistical significance results performed in this paper to support analysis in Section 4.2. Figs. 4–7 illustrate Welch pairwise statistical t -tests significance after Holm correction heatmaps for the analyzed datasets. Tables 9–11 report the direct statistical comparison between MLP and CNN autoencoders on the 28×28 datasets. Each entry indicates the architecture with the better mean value when the difference is statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.01$ after Holm correction. Entries marked as *Tie* indicate that the difference is not statistically significant. For the reconstruction metrics, lower MSE and higher SSIM, PSNR, and NMI are better. For the MIA metrics, lower Δ_{MIA} , TPR@1%FPR, and TPR@5%FPR are better.

Fig. 4: Pairwise statistical significance heatmaps for OrganCMNIST. Green indicates significantly different at $\alpha = 0.01$ after Holm correction; red indicates no significant difference.

Fig. 5: Pairwise statistical significance heatmaps for PneumoniaMNIST. Green indicates significantly different at $\alpha = 0.01$ after Holm correction; red indicates no significant difference.

Table 9: Statistically significant MLP–CNN winners on OrganCMNIST. Each entry reports the architecture with the better mean value when the difference is significant at $\alpha = 0.01$ after Holm correction; *Tie* indicates no significant difference.

Setup	Image Reconstruction				MIA Evaluation		
	MSE↓	SSIM↑	PSNR↑	NMI↑	Δ_{MIA} ↓	TPR@1%↓	TPR@5%↓
ae	CNN	CNN	CNN	CNN	MLP	CNN	MLP
ae-dp	CNN	CNN	CNN	CNN	MLP	CNN	<i>Tie</i>
ae-fl	CNN	CNN	CNN	CNN	MLP	CNN	<i>Tie</i>
ae-dp-fl	CNN	CNN	CNN	CNN	MLP	<i>Tie</i>	MLP
ae-lipi	CNN	CNN	CNN	CNN	MLP	CNN	CNN
<i>CoEvo-DP</i>	CNN	CNN	CNN	CNN	MLP	<i>Tie</i>	MLP

Fig. 6: Pairwise statistical significance heatmaps for RetinaMNIST. Green indicates significantly different at $\alpha = 0.01$ after Holm correction; red indicates no significant difference.

Fig. 7: Pairwise statistical significance heatmaps for large RetinaMNIST. Green indicates significantly different at $\alpha = 0.01$ after Holm correction; red indicates no significant difference.

Table 10: Statistically significant MLP–CNN winners on PneumoniaMNIST. Each entry reports the architecture with the better mean value when the difference is significant at $\alpha = 0.01$ after Holm correction; *Tie* indicates no significant difference.

Setup	Image Reconstruction				MIA Evaluation		
	MSE↓	SSIM↑	PSNR↑	NMI↑	$\Delta_{\text{MIA}} \downarrow$	TPR@1%↓	TPR@5%↓
ae	CNN	CNN	CNN	CNN	MLP	<i>Tie</i>	CNN
ae-dp	CNN	CNN	CNN	CNN	<i>Tie</i>	MLP	<i>Tie</i>
ae-fl	CNN	CNN	CNN	CNN	MLP	CNN	CNN
ae-dp-fl	CNN	CNN	CNN	<i>Tie</i>	CNN	<i>Tie</i>	CNN
ae-lipi	CNN	CNN	CNN	CNN	MLP	CNN	<i>Tie</i>
<i>CoEvo-DP</i>	CNN	CNN	CNN	MLP	CNN	<i>Tie</i>	<i>Tie</i>

Table 11: Statistically significant MLP–CNN winners on RetinaMNIST. Each entry reports the architecture with the better mean value when the difference is significant at $\alpha = 0.01$ after Holm correction; *Tie* indicates no significant difference.

Setup	Image Reconstruction				MIA Evaluation		
	MSE↓	SSIM↑	PSNR↑	NMI↑	$\Delta_{\text{MIA}} \downarrow$	TPR@1%↓	TPR@5%↓
ae	CNN	MLP	CNN	MLP	<i>Tie</i>	<i>Tie</i>	<i>Tie</i>
ae-dp	CNN	MLP	CNN	MLP	<i>Tie</i>	MLP	<i>Tie</i>
ae-fl	CNN	<i>Tie</i>	CNN	MLP	CNN	<i>Tie</i>	<i>Tie</i>
ae-dp-fl	MLP	MLP	MLP	MLP	MLP	MLP	<i>Tie</i>
ae-lipi	CNN	MLP	CNN	MLP	CNN	<i>Tie</i>	<i>Tie</i>
<i>CoEvo-DP</i>	CNN	MLP	CNN	MLP	CNN	MLP	<i>Tie</i>

B Signal propagation and selection pressure results

The experiments were carried out on the DermaMNIST dataset. To study signal propagation, Tables 12 and 13 report quality, privacy, and diversity metrics for different radii with a fixed tournament size $\tau = 2$. To analyze selection pressure, Tables 14, 15, and 16 report the corresponding results for varying tournament sizes τ at fixed radii $r = 2$ and $r = 3$. All values are reported as the mean, with the normalized standard deviation shown in parentheses. Boldface denotes the best-performing configuration when it is statistically better than the remaining configurations for the corresponding metric ($p < 0.01$).

Table 12: Quality and privacy metrics for different radii and $\tau = 2$. Values are reported as mean (normalized standard deviation in %).

r	MSE↓	SSIM↑	PSNR↑	NMI↑	$\Delta_{\text{MIA}} \downarrow$	TPR@1%↓	TPR@5%↓
1	0.66(2.10)	54.08(1.16)	21.81(0.42)	1.21(0.09)	0.01(31.95)	1.00(46.66)	6.00(14.47)
2	0.65(2.35)	53.54(1.26)	21.89(0.47)	1.21(0.08)	0.01(21.79)	1.25(29.64)	6.00(13.45)
3	0.63(2.33)	53.57(1.14)	22.00(0.46)	1.21(0.09)	0.01(32.31)	1.00(39.64)	5.50(14.13)
4	0.64(2.70)	53.32(1.13)	21.99(0.53)	1.21(0.08)	0.01(24.02)	1.00(37.75)	6.00(15.27)

Table 13: Diversity (L_2 distance) for different radii and $\tau = 2$ (mean with normalized standard deviation in parentheses, in %).

r	Encoders	Decoders
1	29.53(39.70)	33.01(34.25)
2	17.84(27.73)	17.53(36.50)
3	17.90(22.27)	16.14(12.94)
4	15.75(29.14)	14.74(20.23)

Tables 12 and 13 show that the communication radius r mainly affects the quality–diversity trade-off of CoEvo-DP when the tournament size is fixed at $\tau = 2$. Increasing r improves pixel-wise reconstruction, with $r = 3$ obtaining the best MSE and PSNR, 0.63(2.33) and 22.00(0.46), respectively, and $r = 4$ remaining statistically competitive. This indicates that propagating information beyond the immediate neighborhood helps disseminate useful encoder–decoder components, although larger radii do not yield a clear additional gain. By contrast, the highest SSIM is achieved with the most local topology, $r = 1$, suggesting that limited communication better preserves structural similarity. NMI and the membership-inference indicators remain essentially stable across radii, so the reconstruction gains obtained with $r = 3$ and $r = 4$ do not correspond to a systematic privacy degradation under the considered metrics.

The diversity results support this interpretation. The smallest radius gives the highest encoder and decoder diversity, whereas larger neighborhoods reduce diversity substantially, especially in the decoder population. Thus, radius controls how quickly information spreads through the ring: local neighborhoods maintain heterogeneous populations and structural similarity, while wider neighborhoods promote convergence and improve error-based reconstruction. Overall,

$r = 3$ provides the most favorable compromise, whereas $r = 1$ favors diversity and SSIM.

Table 14: Quality and privacy metrics for $r = 2$ and different τ . Values are reported as mean (normalized standard deviation in %).

τ	MSE↓	SSIM↑	PSNR↑	NMI↑	Δ_{MIA} ↓	TPR@1%↓	TPR@5%↓
2	0.65(2.35)	53.54(1.26)	21.89(0.47)	1.21(0.08)	0.01(21.79)	1.25(29.64)	6.00(13.45)
3	0.64(2.29)	53.41(0.95)	21.96(0.45)	1.21(0.08)	0.01(28.73)	1.00(33.19)	5.50(18.98)
4	0.64(1.80)	52.91(1.17)	21.99(0.36)	1.21(0.08)	0.01(26.47)	1.25(30.49)	6.00(14.46)
5	0.64(2.61)	53.20(1.52)	21.96(0.52)	1.21(0.08)	0.01(26.03)	1.00(33.01)	6.00(15.46)

Table 15: Quality and privacy metrics for $r = 3$ and different τ . Values are reported as mean (normalized standard deviation in %).

τ	MSE↓	SSIM↑	PSNR↑	NMI↑	Δ_{MIA} ↓	TPR@1%↓	TPR@5%↓
2	0.63(2.33)	53.57(1.14)	22.00(0.46)	1.21(0.09)	0.01(32.31)	1.00(39.64)	5.50(14.13)
3	0.63(1.72)	53.10(1.20)	22.02(0.34)	1.21(0.09)	0.01(24.42)	1.00(34.67)	6.00(14.38)
4	0.63(2.22)	53.06(1.37)	22.02(0.44)	1.21(0.09)	0.01(27.50)	1.00(31.73)	6.25(14.31)
5	0.63(2.60)	52.69(1.46)	22.05(0.51)	1.21(0.09)	0.01(23.12)	1.00(33.74)	6.00(16.65)
6	0.63(1.89)	52.50(1.00)	22.04(0.37)	1.21(0.08)	0.01(23.69)	1.00(33.01)	5.75(16.86)
7	0.63(3.00)	52.67(1.22)	22.03(0.58)	1.21(0.10)	0.01(24.07)	1.00(37.31)	5.75(14.33)

Table 16: Diversity (L_2 distance) for radii $r = 2$ and $r = 3$ (mean with normalized standard deviation in parentheses; normalized values are percentages).

Size (τ)	$r = 2$		$r = 3$	
	Encoders	Decoders	Encoders	Decoders
2	17.84(27.73)	17.53(36.50)	17.90(22.27)	16.14(12.94)
3	18.05(18.22)	17.89(30.99)	16.13(24.25)	15.84(25.06)
4	17.37(24.37)	18.10(24.39)	15.48(24.21)	14.41(15.87)
5	16.07(21.15)	16.64(26.50)	14.42(22.94)	14.21(22.65)
6	—	—	14.93(21.33)	14.18(24.33)
7	—	—	13.40(28.14)	14.06(24.55)

Tables 14, 15, and 16 show that the tournament size τ has a weaker effect on reconstruction error but a clearer effect on structural similarity and diversity. For both $r = 2$ and $r = 3$, MSE, PSNR, NMI, Δ_{MIA} , and the low-FPR TPR values remain within narrow ranges, indicating that selection pressure does not systematically change either reconstruction quality or privacy behavior. The main differences appear in SSIM and diversity: low or moderate tournament sizes, especially $\tau = 2$ and $\tau = 3$, preserve structural similarity and maintain more diverse encoder–decoder populations, whereas larger τ values accelerate convergence and reduce diversity, particularly for $r = 3$. Taken together, these results indicate that low tournament sizes provide the most robust trade-off.